

Synthetic Studies in the Diterpene Series. Part-XI¹. A Synthesis of 7,16-Epoxy-20-norcleistantha- 5(10),6,8,11,13-pentaen-3-one, a Naphthalenic Norditerpene from Velloziaceae

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A synthesis of the title compound (4), a naphthalenic norditerpene recently isolated from Velloziaceae by Brazilian workers, has been achieved using 4,5-dihydro-3-methylnaphtho[1,8-*bc*]pyran (6) as the key intermediate. The latter has been prepared from 4-chromanone through a series of reactions involving Knoevenagel condensation with ethyl cyanoacetate, elaboration of the side chain to 3-substituted-butyric acid, its cyclisation to a tricyclic ketone and aromatisation of the newly formed ring. The dihydronaphthopyran is succinoylated, the keto-acid (8) reduced and the substituted-butyric acid cyclised to 4,5,10,11-tetrahydro-3-methylphenanthro[10,1-*bc*]pyran-9(8*H*)-one (10). The corresponding alcohol is dehydrated, the resultant olefinic product oxidised with *N*-methylmorpholine *N*-oxide (with OsO₄ as catalyst) to the *cis*-diol and the latter submitted to acid catalysed dehydration. Transposition of the ketonic function takes place smoothly leading to 4,5,10,11-tetrahydro-3-methylphenanthro[10,1-*bc*]pyran-9(8*H*)-one (15) which on methylation affords 7,16-epoxy-20-norcleistantha-5(10),6,8,11,13-pentaen-3-one (4), identical with the natural product.

RECENTLY, a group of Brazilian workers have reported the isolation² of two novel diterpenes, veadeirol (1) and veadeiroic acid (2) (Chart 1) from the hexane extract of the stem of *Vellozia flavicans* Martius ex Schultz. The interest of these diterpenes lies in the fact that so far only one natural product, namely, cleistanthol (3) is known³ with the same abnormal skeleton and represents a structurally new diterpene in which the parent hydrocarbon is 14-ethyl-13-methyl-5 β ,10 α -podocarpane. In a subsequent paper⁴, the same workers isolated two related naphthalenic norditerpenes from *V. stipitata* and *V. declinans* having the tetracyclic structures 4 and 5, respectively, which correspond to norcleistanthane nucleus with the angular 10-Me being lost during aromatisation of ring B and with an epoxide ring bridging C-7 and C-16. The dehydro compound (5) may be an artifact being formed by autoxidation of the norditerpene (4). The structures of these novel diterpenes have been determined from spectroscopic data (ir, uv, pmr and cmr) but to our knowledge, no synthetic evidence has so far been adduced. As a part of our programme on the synthesis of naturally occurring diterpenes^{5,6}, we undertook to synthesise these diterpenoids through unambiguous routes. In the present communication, we report the synthesis of the two naphthalenic norditerpenes (4 and 5)⁷ while that of veadeirol (1) and veadeiroic acid (2) will appear in a subsequent paper⁸. Following IUPAC convention⁹, 4 is named

Chart 1

as 7,16-epoxy-20-norcleistantha-5(10),6,8,11,13-pentaen-3-one in place of its original nomenclature⁴ as 4,5,10,11-tetrahydro-3,8,8-trimethylphenanthro[10,1-*bc*]pyran-9(8*H*)-one.

Results

The synthetic strategy was to prepare 4,5-dihydro-3-methylnaphtho[1,8-*bc*]pyran (6), condense

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it with succinic anhydride to afford the keto acid (8) as the major product and reduce it to the substituted-butyrac acid (9) (Scheme 1). This on cyclisation would give the tetracyclic ketone (10) which could be converted into the 2-oxo derivative (12) by reaction with methylmagnesium iodide followed by dehydration and finally oxidation of the olefinic product (11)—a common procedure for the transposition of ketonic group. Methylation of the ketone (12) would furnish the desired norditerpene (4). Alternatively, the tetracyclic ketone (10) on reduction and dehydration would lead to the dihydrophenanthrene (13) which on oxidation under

appropriate condition would give the diol (14). The latter on acid-catalysed dehydration would form the isomeric ketone (15), a β -tetralone analogue which would easily methylate to the dimethylated product (4).

For the synthesis of 4,5-dihydro-3-methylnaphtho[1,8-*bc*]pyran (6), β -phenoxypropionic acid was cyclised to 4-chromanone (16) with polyphosphoric acid¹⁰. The latter was condensed with ethyl cyanoacetate according to a modified procedure of Knoevenagel reaction¹¹ to furnish chroman-4-ylidenecyanoacetate (17) in 77% yield (Scheme 2).

Scheme 1. Reagents : (i) Succinic anhydride, AlCl_3 ; (ii) Zn-Hg , HCl ; (iii) SOCl_2 , Et_3N ; (iv) MeMgI ; (v) $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CO}_2\text{H}$ in CHCl_3 , H_2SO_4 ; (vi) MeI , KOBu^t ; (vii) NaBH_4 , PTSA in C_6H_6 ; (viii) *N*-methylmorpholine *N*-oxide + OsO_4 ; (ix) PTSA in C_6H_6 .

Scheme 2. Reagents : (i) $\text{CH}_3(\text{CN})\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$, NH_4OAc , AcOH ; (ii) Pd-C/H_2 ; (iii) NaOEt , MeI ; (iv) KOH in $\text{HO}(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{OH}$; (v) HCl ; (vi) SOCl_2 , CH_3N_3 , A_2O ; (vii) PPA ; (viii) LiAlH_4 ; (ix) PTSA in C_6H_6 ; (x) S at $240-50^\circ$.

The pmr spectrum showed it to be a mixture of *E* (aryl and CO₂Et on opposite sides) and *Z* isomers, the former predominating to the extent of 80% as exhibited by the two 3-methylene triplets at δ 3.34 and 2.93 for the *E* and *Z* isomers, respectively. The mixture was reduced catalytically to give a diastereoisomeric mixture of substituted-cyanoacetates (**18**) in a ratio of 60 : 40 (determined by pmr). This was directly methylated and the product, again a diastereoisomeric mixture, hydrolysed and decarboxylated to the propionic acid (**19**). The latter, m.p. 65-80°, showed a pmr spectrum having two doublets for α -methyl at δ 1.27 (*J* 7 Hz) and 1.10 (*J* 7 Hz) in approximately 40 : 60 ratio. It was converted into the acid chloride and subjected to Arndt-Eistert homologation procedure¹². The resulting butyric acid (**20**), however, could not be obtained in more than 30% yield. In an alternative approach, the acid (**19**) was reduced with LiAlH₄, the alcohol brominated and the bromide converted into the butyric acid (**20**) via the cyanide with an overall yield of 40%. As expected, the acid (**20**) was also a diastereoisomeric mixture (60 : 40) having m.p. 108-32°.

The foregoing butyric acid (**20**) was cyclised with polyphosphoric acid to 3,3*a*,4,5-tetrahydronaphtho[1,8-*bc*]pyran-1(2*H*)-one (**21**) in 85% yield. This was reduced with LiAlH₄ to the alcohol (**22**) and the latter dehydrated by *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (PTSA) in refluxing benzene. The product on careful dehydrogenation with calculated amount of sulphur furnished 4,5-dihydro-3-methylnaphtho[1,8-*bc*]pyran (**6**) characterised by its pmr spectrum : δ (CDCl₂) 7.60 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, 1-H), 7.40-7.20 (3H, m, ArH), 6.90 (1H, m, 7-H), 4.40 (2H, t, *J* 7 Hz, 5-H₂), 3.10 (2H, t, *J* 7 Hz, 4-H₂) and 2.40 (3H, s, 3-CH₃). In some experiments, traces of 3-methylnaphtho[1,8-*bc*]pyran (as **6** with a double bond between C-4 and C-5) were formed as indicated by the appearance of vinyl protons in pmr. Its formation could be eliminated by addition of equivalent amount of sulphur in two instalments.

The dihydronaphthopyran (**6**) was next submitted to a Friedel-Crafts reaction with succinic anhydride using anhydrous AlCl₃ in nitrobenzene¹³. Two isomeric keto acids, **7** and **8** were obtained in a ratio of 40 : 60 which separated smoothly by fractional crystallisation. The major component, m.p. 183°, turned out to be the desired product (**8**) as confirmed by pmr† : δ (CDCl₂) 11.20 (1H, s, CO₂H), 8.76 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, 1-H), 7.96 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, 8-H), 7.42 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, 2-H), 6.90 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, 7-H), 4.45 (2H, t, *J* 7 Hz, 5-H₂), 3.36, 3.15, 2.82 (3 × 2H, t, *J* 7 Hz, 3 × CH₂) and 2.36 (3H, s, 3-CH₃). The isomeric keto acid (**7**), m.p. 152°, showed a spectrum having peaks at δ 11.20 (1H, s, CO₂H), 7.82 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, 8-H), 7.64 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, 1-H), 7.44 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, 2-H), 7.40 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, 9-H), 4.52 (2H, t, *J* 7 Hz, 5-H₂), 3.46, 3.16, 2.78 (3 × 2H, t, *J* 7 Hz, 3 × CH₂) and 2.40 (3H, s,

3-CH₃). The two lowest field aromatic protons, 1-H in **8** and 8-H in **7** at δ 8.76 and 7.82, respectively helped to assign unambiguously the two structures (1-H in **8** would be much more deshielded by the carbonyl group at the *peri*-position). In contrast, 1-methoxyphenanthrene on being succinoylated under similar condition afforded only one product, acylation taking place exclusively at 4-position. Presumably, the methoxyl group offers steric hindrance to *ortho*-acylation to a much greater extent than OCH₃ group.

The keto acid (**8**) was reduced to the γ -arylbutyric acid (**9**) and the derived acid chloride cyclised intra-molecularly with stannic chloride¹⁴. That the tetracyclic ketone (**10**) had the correct structure was confirmed at this stage by pmr spectrum which showed the following peaks : δ (CDCl₂) 8.00 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, 1-H), 7.60 (1H, s, 7-H), 7.50 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, 2-H), 4.43 (2H, t, *J* 7 Hz, 5-H₂), 3.23 (4H, m, 2 × ArCH₂), 2.74 (2H, t, *J* 7 Hz, 9-H₂), 2.47 (3H, s, 3-CH₃) and 2.27 (2H, m, 10-H₂). The moderately low-field signal of 7-H at δ 7.60 (s) was the result of the combined deshielding effect of 8-oxo and the shielding effect of 6-oxy groups.

The ketone (**10**) was treated with methylmagnesium iodide, the tertiary alcohol dehydrated and the resultant 3,4-dihydrophenanthrene (**11**) oxidised with perbenzoic acid¹⁵. However, the desired β -tetralone (**12**) could not be obtained in isolable yield although its presence could be evidenced in pmr spectrum (a doublet of 8-Me at δ 1.56). Apparently, the more vulnerable naphthalene nucleus with an ether linkage underwent over-oxidation with peracids⁶.

Recently, Hauser and Prasanna¹⁷ have reported the conversion of 2(1*H*)-tetralones from 1(2*H*)-tetralones under relatively mild oxidative condition. Following the method, the tetracyclic ketone (**10**) was reduced with NaBH₄ and the alcohol dehydrated to the dihydrophenanthrene (**13**). The latter on oxidation with *N*-methylmorpholine *N*-oxide with OsO₄ as catalyst afforded a diol in quantitative yield. The diol (**14**) was dehydrated with PTSA in refluxing benzene to furnish in good yield the isomeric tetracyclic ketone (**15**) with the ketonic group transposed. Methylation of the ketone with MeI and KOBu^t afforded a product which on chromatography gave the desired naphthalenic norditerpene (**4**), m.p. 146°. The spectral data (see Experimental) were found to be identical with those reported for the natural product. On being exposed to air for a few days, the ketone (**4**) turned yellow and showed the m.p. and *M*⁺ of the dehydro derivative (**5**). No specimens of the natural compounds could be available for direct comparison.

Experimental

All m.ps. and b.ps. are uncorrected. Ir spectra were taken on a Perkin-Elmer 237 B infra-cord spectrophotometer in CHCl₃, ¹H nmr spectra on a Varian M390 90MHz machine in CDCl₃ unless

† The spectra of compounds **7** and **8** were taken on FT nmr 100 MHz machine.

stated otherwise using SiMe_4 as internal standard and mass spectra with a Hitachi RMU-6L spectrometer at 70 eV using direct inlet system. Homogeneity of compounds were checked by tlc on silica gel-G (Merck) using iodine vapour as visualisation reagent. Petroleum refers to the fraction, b.p. 40-60°. All organic extracts were dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 .

4-Chromanone (16): Polyphosphoric acid prepared from P_2O_5 (120 g) and 89% H_3PO_4 (80 ml) were heated to 110° in an oil-bath. β -Phenoxypropionic acid (34.0 g) was added all at a time and the mixture stirred at 110° for 10 min. The red solution was decomposed with crushed ice and the organic matter extracted with CH_2Cl_2 . On usual work-up, 4-chromanone was obtained as an oil (29.0 g, 90%), b.p. 118°/0.2 mm; ν_{max} 1 680 and 1 600 cm^{-1} ; δ 7.80 (1H, dd, J 7.5 and 1.8 Hz, 5-H), 7.30 (1H, dd, J 7.5 and 1.5 Hz, 7-H), 6.90 (2H, m, 6-H+8-H), 4.45 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, 2- H_a) and 2.70 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, 3- H_a).

Ethyl chroman-4-ylidenecyanoacetate (17): A mixture of 4-chromanone (28.9 g, 0.194 mol), ethyl cyanoacetate (40.0 g), NH_4OAc (10 g), benzene (300 ml) and glacial AcOH (10 ml) was refluxed for 20 h using Dean-Stark water separator. Small portions of NH_4OAc (0.5 g) was added after intervals of 2 h. The mixture was diluted with water (200 ml), the benzene layer separated, the extract washed with 10% aqueous KOH and then with water and dried. On evaporation of the solvent, the residue was fractionally distilled to afford unreacted 4-chromanone (15.0 g), b.p. 115°/2 mm, and ethyl chroman-4-ylidenecyanoacetate (24.0 g, 50%), b.p. 150°/0.5 mm (Found: C, 70.3; H, 4.8%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_3\text{N}$: C, 69.1; H, 4.9%); ν_{max} 2 220 (CN) and 1 680 cm^{-1} (CO_2Et); δ 8.28 (1H, dd, J 7.5 and 1.5 Hz, 5-H), 6.75 (3H, m, ArH), 4.45-4.10 (4H, m, 2- H_a + OCH_2CH_3), 3.32 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, 3- H_a) and 1.30 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, OCH_2CH_3). The unreacted chromanone was once more condensed with ethyl cyanoacetate to afford a further quantity (12.5 g, 25%) of the condensed product.

Ethyl chroman-4-ylcyanoacetate (18): Ethyl chroman-4-ylidenecyanoacetate (9.0 g, 0.037 mol) in ethanol (100 ml) was shaken in an atmosphere of H_2 in the presence of Pd-C (10%, 1.0 g) when theoretical amount of H_2 (ca 900 ml) was absorbed. Ethyl chroman-4-ylcyanoacetate was obtained as a colourless oil (8.6 g, 95%), b.p. 165°/2 mm; ν_{max} 2 238 (CN) and 1 715 cm^{-1} (CO_2Et); δ 7.30-6.72 (4H, m, ArH), 4.40-4.15 (4H, m, 2- H_a + OCH_2CH_3), 3.85 (1H, d, J 6 Hz, α -H), 3.52-3.32 (1H, m, 4-H), 2.00 (2H, t, J 6 Hz, 3- H_a) and 1.20 (3H, m, OCH_2CH_3).

α -Chroman-4-ylpropionic acid (19): The preceding cyanoacetate (34.4 g, 0.14 mol) was added to ethanolic sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (4.0 g, 0.174 mol) in dry ethanol (150 ml). Methyl iodide (75 ml) was then added and the mixture refluxed for 12 h. On usual work-up, ethyl α -chroman-4-ylcyanopropionate was obtained as an oil

(35.1 g, 96%), b.p. 168°/0.2 mm; ν_{max} 2 240 and 1 710 cm^{-1} ; δ 7.32-6.85 (4H, m, ArH), 4.50-4.15 (4H, m, 2- H_a + OCH_2CH_3), 3.62 (1H, t, J 7 Hz, 4-H), 2.15 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, 3- H_a), 1.68 (3H, d, J 8 Hz, 2- CH_3) and 1.20 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, OCH_2CH_3).

The above cyanoester (35.0 g) was added to a solution of KOH (23.0 g) in ethylene glycol (350 ml) and refluxed for 16 h. α -Chroman-4-ylpropionic acid (19) was obtained as a crude solid (22.4 g, 80%), m.p. 60-68°; ν_{max} 1 700 cm^{-1} ; δ 9.20 (1H, s, CO_2H), 7.25-6.85 (4H, m, ArH), 4.28 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, 2- H_a), 3.50 (1H, m, 4-H), 3.20 (1H, m, α -H), 2.08 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, 3- H_a), 1.28 and 1.07 (3H, dd, J 7 Hz, α - CH_3). The acid on recrystallisation from ether-petroleum afforded white needles, m.p. 120-121° (Found: C, 70.1; H, 6.9. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3$: C, 69.9; H, 6.8%).

β -Chroman-4-ylbutyric acid (20): To a solution of the foregoing propionic acid (4.0 g, 0.019 mol) in dry benzene (5 ml), PCl_5 (4.2 g, 0.02 mol) was added. When the reaction subsided, the mixture was heated on a steam-bath for 30 min with occasional stirring. Benzene was removed under reduced pressure. The crude acid chloride (2.5 g, 58%) in dry ether (10 ml) was added to an ethereal solution of diazomethane prepared from nitrosomethylurea (7.0 g) at 5-10°. After 3 h, ether was removed under reduced pressure, the crystalline yellow diazoketone dissolved in dioxane and added dropwise to a mixture of Ag_2O (0.5 g), Na_2CO_3 (1.25 g) and $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ (0.75 g) in water (50 ml) with stirring at 50-60°. Stirring was continued for 1 h more and the temperature raised to 90-100°. The solution was cooled, acidified with dilute HNO_3 and the organic matter extracted with ether. The residue on evaporation of ether and trituration with ether-petroleum (60:40) gave a light yellow solid (1.25 g, 30%), m.p. 108-132° (Found: C, 70.7; H, 7.35. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3$: C, 70.9; H, 7.3%); ν_{max} 1 705 cm^{-1} ; δ 7.20 (4H, m, ArH), 4.30 (2H, m, 2- H_a), 2.90 (1H, m, 4-H), 2.20 (2H, m, α - CH_2), 2.10 (3H, m, 3- H_a + β -H), 1.15 (2H, d, J 7 Hz, β - CH_3) and 0.87 (1H, d, J 7 Hz, β - CH_3).

In an alternative method¹⁸, the propionic acid (19) was reduced with LiAlH_4 in ether to 2-(4-chroman-4-yl)propan-1-ol (95%), b.p. 140°/0.5 mm, which was treated with PBr_3 in CCl_4 to furnish the corresponding bromide (60%), b.p. 135-137°/0.5 mm. The bromide on being refluxed with ethanolic NaCN and a small amount of NaI afforded 2-substituted-butyronitrile (90%), b.p. 105-160°/0.4 mm; ν_{max} 2 240 cm^{-1} , which was hydrolysed with potassium hydroxide in boiling ethylene glycol to furnish β -chroman-4-ylbutyric acid, identical with the one described above. All the intermediate compounds were checked by pmr.

3,3a,4,5-Tetrahydronaphtho[1,8-bc]pyran-1(2H)-one (21): Polyphosphoric acid prepared from P_2O_5 (100 g) and 89% H_3PO_4 (67 ml) were heated on a steam-bath. The afore-mentioned acid (20; 8.0 g) was added to it all at a time and the mixture stirred for 8 min. The red solution was decomposed

with crushed ice, organic matter extracted with CH_2Cl_2 , the extract washed successively with aqueous NaOH and water and dried. The residue on evaporation of the solvent was crystallised from ether to furnish light yellow crystals of the tricyclic ketone (21) (6.8 g, 85%), m.p. 135-41° (Found : C, 77.4; H, 6.8. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$: C, 77.2; H, 6.9%); ν_{max} 1 678 and 1 600 cm^{-1} ; δ 7.70 (1H, dd, J 8 and 2 Hz, 9-H), 7.40-6.98 (2H, m, ArH), 4.40 (2H, m, 5- H_2), 2.90-1.50 (6H, m, $2 \times \text{CH}_2 + 2 \times \text{CH}$), 1.15 (3H, d, J 3- CH_3).

1,2,3,3a,4,5-Hexahydro-3-methylnaphtho[1,8-bc]pyran-1-ol (22) : The above tricyclic ketone (5.8 g, 0.029 mol) was reduced with LiAlH_4 (1.5 g, 0.037 mol) in dry ether (30 ml). The resulting alcohol was obtained in quantitative yield and on crystallisation from ether-petroleum afforded colourless crystals, m.p. 128-132° (Found : C, 76.6; H, 7.9. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2$: C, 76.5; H, 7.85%); ν_{max} 3 500 cm^{-1} .

4,5-Dihydro-3-methylnaphtho[1,8-bc]pyran (6) : The preceding alcohol (5.2 g, 0.025 mol) was refluxed in dry benzene (150 ml) containing PTSA (20 mg) for 10 min. The reaction mixture was cooled, diluted with water, the benzene layer separated, washed and dried. The residue on evaporation of the solvent was distilled to furnish an oil (2.85 g, 60%), b.p. 110-115°/0.3 mm.

The above oil (2.30 g, 0.0123 mol) and powdered sulphur (0.2 g, 0.0061 mol) were heated at 240-250° in a nitrite-nitrate-bath for 10 min. A further quantity of sulphur (0.20 g, 0.0061 mol) was added and heating continued for 15 min. The black residue was taken up in petroleum and passed through an alumina column. The solvent was removed and the residue distilled to furnish pure 4,5-dihydro-3-methylnaphtho[1,8-bc]pyran (6) (1.8 g, 81%), b.p. 128°/0.2 mm (Found : C, 83.7; H, 7.4. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}$: C, 83.9; H, 7.5%); ^1H nmr spectrum discussed in the text.

If any excess of sulphur was used, formation of 3-methylnaphtho[1,8-bc]pyran was detected in pmr spectrum by the appearance of vinyl proton peaks at δ 6.7 (d, J 6 Hz) and 6.0 (d, J 6 Hz).

β -(4,5-Dihydro-3-methylnaphtho[1,8-bc]pyran-9-oyl)-propionic acid (8) and β -(4,5-dihydro-3-methylnaphtho[1,8-bc]pyran-7-oyl)propionic acid (7) : A solution of 4,5-dihydro-3-methylnaphtho[1,8-bc]pyran (6; 1.84 g, 0.010 mol) in nitrobenzene (4 ml) was added to cooled and stirred solution of anhydrous AlCl_3 (2.67 g, 0.020 mol) and succinic anhydride (1.00 g, 0.010 mol) in nitrobenzene (6 ml) at such a rate that the temperature remained below 10°. After the addition was complete, the ice-bath was removed and the dark mixture stirred for 4 h, decomposed with ice and subjected to steam-distillation. The acidic material was taken up in CH_2Cl_2 , dissolved in aqueous NaHCO_3 and regenerated to furnish a solid mass (1.93 g, 68%), m.p. 133-153°. The pmr spectrum showed it to be a 60 : 40 mixture of the isomeric acids 8 and 7. It was dissolved in minimum

quantity of hot CCl_4 and cooled. The first crop gave the keto acid (8) as yellow crystalline solid (0.81 g, 28%), m.p. 183° (Found : C, 71.9; H, 5.6. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$: C, 71.8; H, 5.6%); ν_{max} 1 680 and 1 705 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr spectrum discussed in the text.

The second crop, also a yellow crystalline solid appeared to be the isomeric keto acid (7) (0.67 g, 27%), m.p. 142° (Found : C, 72.0; H, 5.6%); ν_{max} 1 682 and 1 710 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr spectrum discussed in the text.

γ -(4,5-Dihydro-3-methylnaphtho[1,8-bc]pyran-9-yl)-butyric acid (9) : The preceding keto acid (8; 0.35 g, 0.0012 mol), amalgamated zinc wool (2.5 g), water (3 ml), toluene (2 ml) and concentrated HCl (3 ml) were boiled vigorously for 30 h with occasional addition of HCl (1 ml)¹⁹. The cooled mixture was diluted with water (10 ml) and the organic matter extracted with ether (3 \times 30 ml). The combined organic extract was washed with water, dried, solvent removed and the residue crystallised from CCl_4 to afford the butyric acid (9) as white solid (0.20 g, 60%), m.p. 152° (Found : C, 75.7; H, 6.5. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3$: C, 75.55; H, 6.7%); ν_{max} 1 700 cm^{-1} ; δ 9.50 (1H, s, CO_2H), 7.90 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, 1-H), 7.50 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, 2-H), 7.20 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, 8-H), 6.90 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, 7-H), 4.45 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, 5- H_2), 3.15 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, ArCH_2), 2.90 (2H, m, ArCH_2), 2.40 (5H, s+t, 3- $\text{CH}_3 + \text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H}$) and 2.10 (2H, m, CH_2).

Alternatively, the keto acid (8; 0.40 g) was dissolved in ethyl acetate (10 ml) and AcOH (5 ml). Perchloric acid (0.5 g) and Pd-C (10%, 100 mg) were then added and the mixture shaken in an atmosphere of H_2 . The product was worked up in the usual way to give the butyric acid (9), m.p. 152°.

4,5,10,11-Tetrahydro-3-methylphenanthro[10,1-bc]pyran-8(9H)-one (10) : Thionyl chloride (1 ml) was added to a mixture of the preceding butyric acid (9; 0.49 g, 0.0018 mol) in dry ether (15 ml) and pyridine (2 drops) with shaking till the acid dissolved. After 30 min at room temperature, ether and the excess of SOCl_2 were removed under reduced pressure, benzene (2 ml) was added and in turn removed under reduced pressure. A solution of the resulting acid chloride in benzene (5 ml) was cooled in ice, and to it, stannic chloride (0.75 ml) was added. After being swirled for 1 min, the mixture was hydrolysed with ice and HCl. The product was worked up in the usual way and the tetracyclic ketone (10) thus obtained was crystallised from ether-petroleum (0.252 g, 55%), m.p. 116° (Found : C, 80.8; H, 6.5. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2$: C, 80.95; H, 6.3%); ν_{max} 1 680 cm^{-1} ; δ 8.00 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, 1-H), 7.60 (1H, s, 7-H), 7.50 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, 2-H), 4.43 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, 5- H_2), 3.23 (4H, m, $2 \times \text{ArCH}_2$), 2.74 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, 9- H_2) and 2.27 (2H, m, 10- H_2); M^+ 252.

4,5,10,11-Tetrahydro-3,8-dimethylphenanthro[10,1-bc]pyran-9(8H)-one (12) : A solution of the

foregoing ketone (**10**; 0.10 g, 0.0004 mol) in ether (2 ml) was added dropwise to methylmagnesium iodide (0.5 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed on a steam-bath for 1 h and then decomposed with dilute HCl. The crude alcohol was dehydrated by refluxing a benzene solution (25 ml) containing PTSA (2 mg) for 20 min. The resultant 4,5,10,11-tetrahydro-3,8-dimethylphenanthro[10,1-*bc*]pyran (**11**; 0.082 g, 83%) was dissolved in CHCl_3 (5 ml) and cooled to 0°. A solution of perbenzoic acid (0.044 g, 0.00032 mol) in CHCl_3 (6 ml) was added in cold. After storing overnight in a refrigerator, the solution was washed with aqueous NaOH and then with water. The residue after the removal of solvent was refluxed with a mixture of methanol (1 ml), water (5 ml) and concentrated H_2SO_4 (1 ml) for 1.5 h. The product on usual work-up furnished a gum, glc of which showed it to be a complex mixture. The presence of the ketone (**12**) as a product, however, was evidenced by the 8-Me signal in pmr spectrum as a doublet at δ 1.56 (J 7 Hz). The compound could not be isolated in pure state by chromatography.

4,5,10,11-Tetrahydro-3-methylphenanthro[10,1-*bc*]pyran (13): Sodium borohydride (7.6 mg) was added to a magnetically stirred solution of the ketone (**10**; 0.10 g, 40 mmol) in 95% ethanol (2 ml). The reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 15 min and then worked up as usual. The product 4,5,8,9,10,11-hexahydro-3-methylphenanthro[10,1-*bc*]pyran-8-ol was taken up in benzene (5 ml) and the solution refluxed with the addition of PTSA (2 mg) until tlc showed complete absence of the alcohol. The benzene solution was washed with aqueous NaHCO_3 , then with water, dried and the solvent evaporated to afford the tetrahydropyran (**13**; 0.07 g, 75%), m.p. 57°. It was used in the next operation without further purification.

4,5,8,9,10,11-Hexahydro-3-methylphenanthro[10,1-*bc*]pyran-8,9-diol (14): To a magnetically stirred solution of *N*-methylmorpholine *N*-oxide²⁰ (0.035 g, 30 mmol) in water (0.5 ml), acetone (0.5 ml) and *t*-butanol (0.5 ml), was added OsO_4 (5 mg) in CCl_4 (0.5 ml) followed by the above-mentioned olefin (**13**; 0.060 g) in acetone (0.5 ml). The mixture was stirred overnight, diluted with water and extracted with ethyl acetate. The extract was washed successively with 1% aqueous NaHSO_3 (5 ml), 5% aqueous NaHCO_3 (5 ml) and water. After evaporation of the solvent, the residue was chromatographed on a silica gel column using CH_2Cl_2 as eluent. The *cis*-diol (**14**) was obtained as a crude solid (0.041 g, 60%), m.p. 77°. It was used directly in the next operation.

4,5,10,11-Tetrahydro-3-methylphenanthro[10,1-*bc*]pyran-9(8H)one (15): The preceding diol (35 mg) was dissolved in dry benzene (5 ml) containing PTSA (10 mg) and refluxed for 15 min with azeotropic removal of water. The product on usual work-up afforded the ketone (**15**; 26 mg, 80%), m.p. 110-113°; ν_{max} 1 710 cm^{-1} .

7,16-Epoxy-20-norcleistantha-5(10),6,11,13-pentaen-3-one (4): The above ketone (**15**; 25 mg) was refluxed with KOBU^{\dagger} prepared from potassium (7 mg) and *t*-butanol (2 ml) in an atmosphere of N_2 till the solid dissolved. To the cooled solution, methyl iodide (0.5 ml) was added and the mixture refluxed for 16 h with occasional addition of methyl iodide. White inorganic salt separated, *t*-butanol was removed under reduced pressure and the product worked up in the usual way and thoroughly chromatographed on a column of silica gel under N_2 using CHCl_3 as eluent. It was finally recrystallised from petroleum to afford the norditerpene as colourless crystals (**4**; 12 mg, 55%), m.p. 146° (Found: C, 81.3; H, 7.3. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3$: C, 81.4; H, 7.1%); λ_{max} (EtOH) 225 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.68), 244 (4.70), 308 (3.90), 323 (3.85) and 340 (3.70); ν_{max} 1 710 cm^{-1} ; δ 7.72 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, 1-H), 7.30 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, 2-H), 6.85 (1H, s, 7-H), 4.40 (2H, t, J 6 Hz, 5- H_2), 3.40 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, 11- H_2), 3.20 (2H, t, J 6 Hz, 4- H_2), 2.80 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, 10- H_2), 2.40 (3H, s, 3-Me) and 1.50 (6H, s, 8- Me_2). Some minor differences were noticed in the spectrum in the nature of multiplicity from that reported by Pinto *et al.*⁴. Otherwise, all the spectral data appeared to be identical with those of the natural product.

The colourless compound **4** when kept in powdered form in air, furnished the dehydro form (**5**), m.p. 120-122°. Mass spectra of the two compounds, **4** and **5** showed molecular ion peaks at 280 and 278, respectively.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (B.M.) is grateful to the authorities of Midnapore College, West Bengal, for granting study leave and to U.G.C., New Delhi, for a Fellowship. The authors are indebted to Dr. S. C. Pakrashi, I.I.C.B., Calcutta, for kindly helping with some of the 100 MHz ^1H nmr spectra and to Dr. N. P. Daw, I.I.T., Kharagpur, for recording the 90 MHz.

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